

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Malaysia: An Introduction

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Sources of Revenue

In general terms, Malaysian local authorities derive their revenue from three main sources:

- local taxation in the form of property assessments or the equivalent (about 51 per cent);
- rents and fees for services, and licences (about 32 per cent); and
- fiscal transfers from state and federal governments, for example for road maintenance or specific development projects (about 17 per cent).

These sources will be examined in more detail in what follows.

The general provision for the revenue of Malaysia's local government is the Local Government Act 1976 (LGA), Section 39. The Ministry of Housing and Local Government (MHLG) has classified local government's sources of revenue (i.e., those falling under the first two points above) into six categories as follows:

- assessment rates;
- fees for licences and permits;
- rentals;
- government grants;
- car parking charges, planning fees, compounds, fines and interest;
- loans (from higher levels of government/financial institutions).²⁹

Taxes can only be levied under federal law and so the federal government collects most types of tax receipts, such as income tax, export tax and road tax. Thus, the proportion of total government revenue collected by local governments is relatively small, at 3.4 per cent in 2013.³⁰ Still, tax revenues still represent the greatest share of income for local authorities. Assessment tax, which is a property tax collected on the basis of the annual assessment of rental value or the value-added (selling price) of the property, is an important source of revenue for local authorities. The LGA sets a ceiling on the tax of 35 per cent of annual value or 5 per cent of value-added of a holding. Taxation rates can be varied according to the use and location of the property. Thus, the amount of revenue that can be collected from the

²⁹ Ahmad Yunus, 'United Cities and Local Governments Country Profile: Malaysia' (UCLG 2016) 8-9. And see Nurul Faezah Mohd Talib and others, 'Transparency in Malaysia Local Government Administration. The Overview of Internally Generated Revenue (IGR)' (2017) 1 *International Journal of Business and Management* 22.

³⁰ Yunus, 'United Cities and Local Governments Country Profile: Malaysia', above, 8-9.

assessment tax depends on the property's level of physical development. Assessment tax revenue, therefore, varies with the taxation rate, annual value (or value-added), and number and type of holdings.³¹

However, due to the over-reliance of most councils on these assessment taxes, weaker local authorities, and especially rural ones, are often still strapped for financial resources in carrying out their operations.³² As a result, these authorities rely heavily on grants from the federal government or the state.³³ In this regard, a good relationship between the local government and the federal and state government is necessary to obtain funding on a consistent basis. It is at this point that the political patronage system becomes very important for local government, and there are instances of deliberate political partisanship in funding allocations.

Financial grants from federal and state governments include, but are not limited to:

- annual equalisation grants;
- launching grants;
- development project grants;
- road maintenance grants;
- balancing grants.³⁴

Annual equalisation grants, available to all Peninsular Malaysian states, serve to compensate the difference between a local authority's fiscal capacities and fiscal needs. These grants are channelled by the federation to local authorities through the state, in accordance with the State Grant (Maintenance of Local Authorities) Act 1981. The formula used is set by the MHLG. This goes some way towards compensating rural councils whose property assessments will tend to be rather lower than urban ones.³⁵

Launching grants are provided by the state to local authorities for restructuring purposes: to purchase new equipment for service extensions or to undertake infrastructure development projects. Like the others, these grants have to be approved by the MHLG. The size of the grants to a particular local authority depends on factors such as land area, population and expected revenue.

Development project grants are funds made available to all local authorities for the implementation of socio-economic projects, encompassing infrastructure projects, social facilities, cleanliness, beautification, purchase of equipment and machinery, recreational parks and sanitary projects.

³¹ Yunus, 'United Cities and Local Governments Country Profile: Malaysia', above.

³² *ibid.*

³³ *ibid.*; and Talib and others, 'Transparency in Malaysia Local Government Administration', above.

³⁴ *ibid.*

³⁵ Talib and others, 'Transparency in Malaysia Local Government Administration', above.

Balancing grants are offered by the state to cover rising operational expenditure costs, such as from the increase of pay levels negotiated by the federal government for the public sector. Smaller local councils can also choose to utilise these grants to aid in minor development projects.

Licence fees are a major source of income for local authorities, and are levied by local authorities to regulate trading activities within their jurisdictional areas. The LGA gives wide powers to local authorities to register, license and regulate trade, commerce and industry. The charges imposed by local governments vary according to the category of licence.³⁶

Fees and service charges are levied when local authorities carry out various activities and provide facilities for the local community. They can also impose charges for services rendered. In general, these sources produce no less than 10 per cent of the total revenue of local authorities. Examples include fees and charges for planning processing under the TCPA, car parking, and use of tools and recreational facilities such as swimming pools.³⁷

Federal funding for local government also targets needy areas, which are invariably rural. For example, in April 2021 the MHLG allocated RM 6.3 million for tourism and economic development in Kuala Langat, a rural area in Southwest Selangor.³⁸

Based on figures from fiscal year 2016/17, subnational governments raised in total approximately USD 676 purchasing power parity (PPP) per capita, of which state and local governments, respectively, accounted for 65 per cent and 35 per cent. The total revenues correspond to about 2.5 per cent of the country's GDP, which is relatively low compared to both federal and unitary countries in Southeast Asia (only Cambodia reports lower figures).

In fiscal year 2016, local government revenues amounted to RM 10.42 billion (about Euro 2.1 billion, or USD 235 PPP per capita), of which 10.5 per cent corresponded to transfers made to local governments and the remaining 89.5 per cent was locally-raised revenue, as discussed above. Details of local revenues are available only at an aggregate level, which does not allow discernment between taxes/tariffs and fees as sources of revenue. In practice states as well as local governments have financial difficulties, and do not have the capacity at any significant level to financially support local governments, which mainly rely on federal funding to supply shortfall and mount special projects.

All subnational governments are allowed to borrow for a period not exceeding five years. In fiscal year 2016, subnational debt corresponded to 0.4 per cent of the country's GDP and 0.6 per cent of the general government outstanding debt. Local government debt remains low, corresponding to 0.2 per cent of total subnational debt in fiscal year 2016. According to Article

³⁶ *ibid.*

³⁷ *ibid.* See also the case study on SPICE in report section 5 on intergovernmental relations of local governments.

³⁸ 'Housing and local government ministry approves RM6.3m fund to Kuala Langat' (*Malay Mail*, 15 April 2021) <<https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2021/04/15/housing-and-local-government-ministry-approves-rm6.3m-fund-to-kuala-langat/1966752>>.

111 of the Constitution, state governments, except those of Sabah and Sarawak, are only allowed to borrow from the federal government, with its prior approval. According to the Local Government Act 2006, local governments may, with the approval and under conditions agreed by the state government, contract loans. Within the powers of local governments, such loans may be used for the acquisition of land, the construction of public buildings, for carrying out permanent works, for providing or maintaining plant equipment and vehicles and to pay off existing loans.

Statistics reported by Lim Mah Hui for Penang Council (MPIP) during 2007-17³⁹ indicate that over this period the proportion of tax revenue decreased from 62 per cent to 54 per cent, while non-tax revenue increased from 28 per cent to 41 per cent, and non-tax receipts (federal and state government transfers) decreased from 10 per cent to 5 per cent. Average annual revenue growth over the period was 5.9 per cent and the total revenue for 2017 was RM 359 million (Euro 72 million). Penang is one of the wealthiest local authorities. There are no equivalent figures available for district councils.

The result of a lack of adequate resourcing has been an understandable emphasis on maintaining services rather than on development and response to changing needs. This affects rural areas more than urban areas. Little has been done, despite much rhetoric, to improve provision of services at similar or lower cost by privatising local government services.⁴⁰ There is consequently a deficit in effective enforcement of relevant laws, authorities seemingly unable in many ways to fully utilise their powers. This is especially the case with collection of local rates.

One particular problem that seems capable of being easily addressed is that, since local government employees do not form part of the public service as such but are simply employees of the local authority in question, they cannot simply be transferred to other local authorities. Thus, meritorious employees can get stuck at middle levels of promotion for years, there being few opportunities for promotion, and may leave the service for better prospects elsewhere; mediocre employees on the other hand tend to remain where they are.

Problems of enforcement of local government laws are widespread and are attributable to lack of enforcement officers, itself a function of local government finance.

The National Finance Council

In a federal system, mention needs to be made of the National Finance Council (NFC), which impacts on local government in that in large measure it affects state finance and therefore in part determines available funding to be transferred to local authorities. Large development

³⁹ Lim Mah Hui, *Local Democracy Denied? A Personal Journey into Local Government in Malaysia* (SIRDC 2020) 70-1.

⁴⁰ Ahmad Atory Hussain and Malike Brahim, 'Administrative Modernisation in the Malaysian Local Government: A Study in Promoting Efficiency, Effectiveness and Productivity' (2006) 14 *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 51.

projects are also usually funded by cooperation between the state and local, as well as federal, government.

The role of the NFC is to look into the various aspects of financial management of the states and to coordinate federal-state finance. The Federal Constitution (Article 108(4)) stipulates that it shall be the duty of the federal government to consult the NFC in respect of, inter alia: the making of federal grants to the states; the assignment of the whole or any portion of the proceeds of the federal government to the states; the annual loan requirements of the federation and the states and the exercise by the federation and the states of their borrowing powers; and the making of loans to any of the states.⁴¹ This consultation is non-binding.⁴² The NFC comprises the Prime Minister (PM) as chairman, one other federal minister designated by the PM; and one representative from each of the states, appointed by the Ruler/Governor. The NFC meets at least once a year, or when called by the PM, or requested by at least three states.⁴³

As a result of the limited revenue base of state governments, many states are dependent on federal transfers and loans to finance their expenditure.⁴⁴ Thus the NFC plays a crucial role in facilitating negotiations between the federal and state government concerning federal financial and funding issues i.e. federal sponsored development projects, transfer of financial resources (grants and loans) to the states.⁴⁵

The NFC will also be consulted in other issues to ensure that both the federal and state governments have influence in these areas. One example is in the establishment of a national development plan⁴⁶ provided for under Article 92 of the Federal Constitution, where the NFC will have to be consulted before Parliament can give effect to the development plan.

In the most recent NFC meeting,⁴⁷ the federal government agreed to implement four enhancements to allocations channelled in various forms of grants and support to the state governments for 2021. During the meeting, the Ministry of Finance said that the federal government was aware that the state governments were experiencing a very drastic reduction in revenue post-Covid-19. This impacts, in turn, local government finance. Hence, one enhancement provided an allocation of RM 260 million (Euro 57.1 million) to the state

⁴¹ Abdul Rahim Anuar, 'Fiscal Decentralization in Malaysia' (2000) 41 *Hitotsubashi Journal of Economics* 85.

⁴² Gary Marks, 'Country Profile – Malaysia' (*University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*, 16 May 2021) <<https://garymarks.web.unc.edu/data/regional-authority-2/>>.

⁴³ Anuar, 'Fiscal Decentralization in Malaysia', above, 92.

⁴⁴ *ibid.* 94.

⁴⁵ *ibid.* 85.

⁴⁶ Plan for the development, improvement or conservation of the natural resources of a development area, the exploitation of such resources, or the increase of means of employment in the area.

⁴⁷ 'Federal Govt Implements Four Enhancements to Grants, Support for States' (*Official Portal of Ministry of Finance*, 6 May 2021) <<https://www.mof.gov.my/en/news/press-citations/federal-govt-implements-four-enhancements-to-grants-support-for-states>>.

governments to help them implement small-scale projects at the grassroots, that is, at local government, level.

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